

WORK EMPOWERMENTS AS CORRELATES OF TEACHERS JOB COMMITMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated work empowerments as correlates of teachers job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study was guided by two research questions and two null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlation research design. The population of the study consisted of 5,412 respondents which comprised 263 principals and 5,149 teachers' in the 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. The sample of this study comprised 803 respondents which consisted of 263 principals' and 540 teachers' randomly drawn using stratified and simple random sampling technique. The instruments for data collection were two questionnaires structured by the researcher, titled Work Empowerments Questionnaire (WEQ), and Teachers Job Commitment Questionnaires (TJCQ). These instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts, two from Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation, all from Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The construct validity of the instruments was also established. Cronbach Alpha method was used to determine the reliabilities of the instruments. The reliability yielded the average coefficient value of 0.76 for work empowerments questionnaire and 0.85 for teachers' job commitment questionnaire which was considered adequate for the study. Eight hundred and three (803) copies of questionnaires were administered by the researcher with six briefed research-assistants by direct administration and collected on the spot. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions while the Hypotheses were tested using test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The findings of the study revealed among others that there is a very strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. It was also found a very strong positive and significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that: principals should give teachers more opportunities to participate in decision- making so as to increase their level of commitment to their job that would in turn improve students' learning outcome in secondary schools.

Keywords: Work Empowerments, Teachers, Job Commitment, Decision-Making, Professional Growth

Introduction

Teachers are one of the vital resources in every educational institution. This is based on the fact that teachers are the professionals who instruct, train and guide students to acquire desirable skills, knowledge and character. Obiekwe, Joseph and Madudili (2024) opined that teachers play important roles in ensuring the success of the education system by translating the educational goals into knowledge and skill, and transferring them to students in the classroom. Thus, the quality of teaching in any institution is intrinsically tied to the job commitment of teachers.

Teachers' job commitment is the act of teaching staff exhibiting devotion to their duties to attain predetermined objectives of education. Teachers' job commitment is described by Adebayo and Ileuma (2023), as the level of dedication and effort that members of teaching staff put in discharging their job. According to Musabwayire and Sikubwabo (2024), teachers' commitment is the loyalty and emotional bond that members of teaching staff demonstrate toward their work. Cervanez and Francisco (2024) listed three dimension of teachers' job commitment to include: continuance, affective and normative. Continuance commitment is committed with dedication to duties due to virtue of the costs associated with getting another job. Nwokolo and Ajufo (2024) pointed out that affective commitment on the other hand is a positive feeling of identification with attachment to, and involvement in the work organization, while normative commitment refers to the internalized pressure to align an individual's goals to the organizational values and interests.

Committed teachers have strong passion for teaching, arrive early to work and work hard to cover their scheme of work for the term. Ibezim (2024) maintained that teachers who are committed to their job are punctual to work, willing to prepare their lesson notes and plans, deliver instructions at the expected period, cover their scheme of work/diary before the end of every term administer examinations and process the results of students at the appropriate time. However, some teachers seem to exhibit absenteeism, tardiness and other forms of professional misconduct which are obvious signs of low job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. To buttress this, Ibezim and Ikediugwu (2023) noted that the scenarios of some teachers sneaking out of school during official hours to attend to their personal affairs, presenting ill-prepared lessons, exhibiting of poor role models to students, absenting from school and classes makes one wonders if they are committed to their job in secondary schools in Anambra State. The principals could play a pivotal role to job commitment of teachers through empowering them.

Empowerment is an outcome of decision- making access, value-added status, knowledge and skills of teachers. Chan and Berkan (2017) opined that empowerment involves working together in terms of delegating work and power to encourage people to become more involved in making-decisions and trusting individuals to have the skills to put their ideas into practices. Empowerment demands that people gain the knowledge, proficiency, and power needed to influence, therefore empowerment becomes the indispensable in any educational reform. Empowerment suggested real changes in one's professional expertise, rising autonomy, and involvement in decision- making processes. Similarly, also Kimwarye, et.al (2014) asserted that an empowered individual has the skills and knowledge to act or improve in a positive way. Hence, empowered teachers believed confidently in their knowledge, skills and actions at the workplace, therefore, teachers' empowerment was synonymous to teachers' leadership in school setting. Teacher empowerment is also perceived as opportunities for shared decision-making, improved professional status, enhancing schools to become a more attractive place for students,

building relationships on the principles of trust and creating excellent communication among teachers.

Empowering teachers within their schools represents a great avenue for cultivating accomplished teachers, providing them with the required autonomy and freedom that make it possible for them to work effectively for the benefit of all concerned (Muhammad, 2014). Teacher empowerment is an effort to increase professional legal responsibility of teachers in school (Muhammad, 2014). It guarantees the effective performance of teachers' jobs through involvement in decisions. Teachers' empowerment is to take charge for one's own growth to solve situational hurdles. It became an important encouraging model in educational reform that concerns with teacher leadership. It does this by giving teachers more power and making them more creative. Teacher empowerment in education cannot be underestimated. Calibayan (2015), defined empowerment as the capability of teachers to take charge of their personal, professional development and growth and to resolve their own problems while in the school systems, create opportunities for competence to be developed and displayed, increase the capacity to distribute roles in decision-making as well as to increase opportunities for meaningful collective participation from teachers. Teacher empowerment consists of six dimensions, namely status, professional growth, self-efficacy, decision making, impact, and autonomy in scheduling (Rinehart & Short, in Suhaili et al, 2020). For this reason, Bogler and Nir (2012) claimed that empowering teachers and building a supportive environment at a school is believed to be a viable solution to problems related to educational effectiveness. Through teacher empowerment, teachers develop their own competence and self-discover their potential and limitations. Similarly, In'am (2015) stated that teachers can be empowered by teachers' involvement in making decisions. Additionally, Kimwarye, *et. al* (2014), stated that teachers' problem solving abilities can be developed by participating in collaborative decision-making processes. Decision-making is a mental process in which an individual conducts mental activity in order to achieve a goal or solve a problem. The process of decision-making is practically applicable to all aspects of administrative organization. Any thought in the administrative process should focus on the principles and methods of decision-making. Therefore, decision-making process is a series of steps and procedures that ultimately lead to the selection of the best alternative solutions, and the issuance of orders for their implementation. Memar and Darwish (2013) defined decision-making skills as "the ability of the individual to reach a solution to the problem they face, in light of both the available possibilities and personal outlook, so that this solution is applicable and implementable without causing any other problem; psychological, social or economic.

Professional growth refers to teachers' perceptions that the school will provide them with the opportunities to grow and develop as professionals, to learn continuously and to expand knowledge and skills through the work-life in school (Abdulrahman, 2015). He further pointed out that professional development practices through seminar, in-service training or workshops offer one of the most promising ways for improving classroom instruction. Organizing in-service training for teachers helps to equip them with emerging trend and strategies in the teaching profession. If an individual is equipped on the job through development programmes, it will be reflected in the job commitment. Teachers can only put in their best, if their professional needs to carry out their functions/duties are provided through professional growth.

Teachers seem not to be adequately empowered to carry out their duties in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Obiekwe, Thompson and Ogbo (2023) noted that most principals in some cases in Anambra State appear less concerned in providing the needed mentorship and seem not to encourage teachers to attend conferences and workshops.

Consequently, they added that most teachers appear not to be equipped with relevant and up-to-date knowledge, skills, abilities, and competencies needed to meet their professional challenges and provide meaningful education to students in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Uzogor and Nwankwo (2020) noted that teachers are not adequately involved in decision making process in public secondary schools in Anambra State. They added that the exclusion of teachers in decision-making process has contributed to poor cooperation, misunderstanding and unwillingness to implement most decisions reached in public secondary schools in Anambra State. It is these problems that prompted the investigation into work empowerments as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this study was to examine work empowerments as correlates of teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the extent of relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Find-out the extent of relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of the relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. What is the extent of the relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in public secondary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

Correlational research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study comprised 7,027 teachers in 5,412 respondents which comprised 263 principals and 5,149 teachers in 263 public secondary schools in Anambra State. Stratified and simple random sampling techniques were used to draw 803 respondents which consisted of 263 principals and 540 teachers for the study. Two sets of instruments: Work Empowerments Questionnaire (WEQ) and Teachers Job Commitment Questionnaires (TJCQ) were used for data collection. WEQ contains 20 items arranged in three clusters namely: I, II and III. Cluster 1 contained 10 items on decision-making and cluster II which focused on professional growth had 10 items. TJCQ contained 20 items which measured the job commitment of teachers. All the items of the two instruments are structured on a four point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instruments were subjected to face validation by three experts who are lecturers, two from Educational Management and one from Measurement and Evaluation in the Department of Educational Foundations, all from Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus, Anambra State. The construct validity of the instruments was also established. Cronbach alpha method was used for a test of internal consistencies of the instruments which yielded overall coefficient value of 0.76 for WEQ and 0.85 for TJCQ respectively.

The instruments were administered by the researcher and five research assistants. A total of 803 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 736 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 91 percent return rate. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and test hypotheses. The research questions were interpreted using the coefficient r and the size of the relationship recommended by Alsagr (2021), as follows:

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Weak correlation
.20- .39	Fair correlation
.40- .69	Moderate correlation
.70- .89	Strong correlation
.90- .1.00	Very strong correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p -value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p -value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05 the null hypothesis was accepted.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the extent of relationship between decision- making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Summary of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the extent of Correlation between decision- making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Decision- making	Teachers job commitment	Remark
Decision- making	Pearson Correlation	1	0.92**	Very strong positive relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.92**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 1 above showed a very strong positive relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with ' r ' = 0.92** and $N = 736$.

This revealed positive correlation coefficient value of 0.92 indicated that there is a very strong positive relationship existing between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Summary of Pearson product moment Correlation Coefficient analysis on the extent of relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

		Correlations		
		Professional growth	Teachers job commitment	Remark
Professional growth	Pearson Correlation	1	0.94**	Very strong relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.94**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The summary result of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient from the Table 2 above showed a very strong positive relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, with 'r' =0.94** and N =736. This revealed positive correlation coefficient value of 0 .94 indicated that there is a very strong positive relationship existing between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Table 3: Test of Significance of Pearson-Moment Correlation Coefficient of the relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Decision -making	Teachers job commitment	Remark
Decision-making	Pearson Correlation	1	0.92**	Significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.92**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson- Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 3 above showed a significant relationship between decision-making and teachers'

job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.92^{**}$.n =736 and p-value = 0.000 .Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: Test of Significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on the relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State

		Correlations		
		Professional growth	Teachers job commitment	Decision
Professional growth	Pearson Correlation	1	0.94 ^{**}	Significant relationship
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00	
	N	736	736	
Teachers job commitment	Pearson Correlation	0.94 ^{**}	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00		
	N	736	736	

^{**}. Correlation is significant at the 0.05level (2-tailed).

The result of the test of significance of Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient from Table 4 above showed a significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State with $r = 0.94^{**}$.n =736 and p-value = 0.000. Since p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05, the study rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State.

Discussion of Finding

The finding from the study showed a very strong positive and significant relationship between decision-making and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. This finding is as a result of principals and teachers agreeing that involvement in decision-making made teachers understand what information can be disclosed, take responsibility of their actions, consider the consequences of their decisions, consider the risks of decisions, apply regulations taking into considering the best practices, apply regulations in account of best practice, understand confidentiality of information, understand what information can not be disclosed. This finding showed that decision-making process helped teachers in selecting the best most preferred and workable action among other options or alternative courses of action available for solving problems and the achievement of an objective. The finding of this study is in consonance with Sharma (2016) who examined the attributes of school teachers' leadership qualities and capacities in Malaysia. The study examined the relationship of teachers' perception of the leadership capacities of their teachers to the leadership qualities of empathy, decision- making, time management, comfort etc. The findings showed that the teachers were perceived to be having strong leadership capacities and strong level of leadership qualities. However there is strong and positive relationship between perception of teachers on leadership capacities and leadership qualities of teachers. Menka (2016) compared the decision-making skills of government and private secondary

schools as well as male and female secondary school teachers. The study was a descriptive survey research design. This study despite that government school teachers' decision-making are more significant than private school teachers. On the other hand there is no significant difference between decision-making skills on the bases of gender. The reason behind the first result might be government school teachers are more independent than private school teachers because former have to implement the policy on the other hand later have to follow the instruction of the management.

The finding showed a very strong positive and significant relationship between professional growth and teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. These findings showed that when investments are made on teacher's career through professional growth, it leads to organizational improvements targeted at teams of teachers, schools, or the entire system. Through attending conferences, teachers absorb the energy of like-minded individuals, get knowledge that enhances their performances in the class, have sufficient training to fully utilize instructional technology, teachers' knowledge increases, deepens teachers' content knowledge, enhances teachers' ability to implement instructional strategies that meet diverse student learning needs, are educated on their responsibilities to the school, responsibilities on the students are properly highlighted, teachers are opportune to be thought by different speakers on measures to affect teaching, learn from other scholars / professional experience in meeting. These findings are similar to findings of Imo, *et.al* (2013) that investigated the influence of staff development programmes on secondary school teachers' job performance in Uyo Metropolis, Nigeria. Whose Findings showed that teachers who participated in staff development programmes like workshop, seminar, conference among others were more effective in their job performance than those who did not, in terms of knowledge of subject matter, classroom management, teaching methods and evaluation of students' work. These findings are similar to findings of Key, *et.al* (2013) conducted a study on professional growth and teachers' job effectiveness in Cross River State. The study was a descriptive survey design. A sample size of 600 students was used to rate teachers in their teaching effectiveness. The researchers found out that teachers' attendance at workshops correlate significantly with their teaching effectiveness in terms of use of instructional materials, presentation of lesson, classroom management, student evaluation and professional qualities.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it is concluded that work empowerments have very strong and significant relationship with teachers' job commitment in Public Secondary Schools in Anambra State. Work empowerments are means of encouraging teachers to participate in decision-making and developing their skills which improve their job commitment. Work empowerments of teachers are indispensable in secondary schools for improving teaching and learning to achieve predetermined goals and objectives.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were based on the findings of this study

1. Principals should give teachers more opportunities to participate in decision-making so as to increase their level of commitment to their job that would in turn improve students' learning outcome in secondary schools.
2. Adequate funds should be provided by Ministry of Education for teachers' professional growth for their sensitization to new trends in the teaching profession.

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